

Introduction: The diversity of geomorphological features of planetary bodies from global scale to 10 meters scale can be encompassed using the multifractal theory [1,2]. This powerful tool allows to aggregate the diversity of roughness in a very limited number of parameters and allows to facilitate comparative planetology. Here we examine the lunar topography to decipher the geological processes creating its particular roughness properties.

Data: We used the LOLA dataset [A] at global scale down to 118 meter spatial resolution.

Methodology: Planetary topographies all exhibit fractal power laws through their roughness at different scales and moments. Several approaches have been developed to estimate the multifractal properties: Mean Haar Fluctuations [6] (MHF, also sometimes called simply Haar analysis), Trace Moments (TM), and double Trace Moments (2TM) [3,4]. Together, these tools offer a detailed and reliable framework for characterizing the fractal nature of planetary landscapes. In previous similar study only Mean Haar Fluctuations (MHF) has been used to study the Moon roughness, this motivated our work using a more robust and accurate method called Double Trace Moment (2TM).

Figure 1: Moon topography. Top: the original topography. Bottom: the effect of H is removed, only the multifractal nature of the topography remains.

When looking at the fractal power law through the roughness, the FIF (fractionally integrated fluxes) multifractal model [5] describes its behavior across moments q and scales λ as $\xi_\lambda(q) = qH - \frac{C_1}{\alpha-1}(q^\alpha - q)$. From this definition the topography can then be de-

scribed by three fundamental parameters (α , C_1 and H). The parameter α , represents the prominence of peaks (topographic mounts), C_1 how sparsely these peaks are and H can be visualized as the effect of accumulating dust and as the erosion of peaks. The topography is said to be monofractal when $C_1 < 0.05$ (no intermittency) and multifractal when $C_1 > 0.05$ (with intermittency).

To study this multifractality, the average resulting fluctuations at each scale can be statistically characterized across multiple moments, the standard method is to evaluate the q^{th} statistical moments, within $0 < q < \alpha$ [7]. We used the 2TM to retrieve the parameters α and C_1 , while the MHF was used to study the power-law parameter (H).

Furthermore, the Power Spectral Density is also a valuable tool to study the field statistics and see power scaling law (e.g. Figure 2 with the regimes A and B). From it, the smoothness H can be derived of the slope from the fitting linear curve (in red) [8].

Results: The MHF analysis (see Figure 2) shows a two-regime behavior, as previously described [1,2,9] The transition regime is around ~ 30 km. We identified domain A with $\lambda < 16$ km and domain B with $\lambda > 100$ km..

Figure 2: EMF and Power Spectral Density of LRO LOLA DEM 118m across scales λ between 3760m and 272km. The black dots come from the full DEM, the gray dots come from 2 individual regimes filtered and the red line their respective fitting curves.

This two regimes were previously study through the MHF, giving in results a dichotomy in the multifractal behavior of the roughness. We propose here to study it through a more robust method called the Double Trace Moment. Figure 1 shows the effect of remove H in the 2D field. Figure 3 illustrates the last step of the 2TM where α and C_1 are calculated.

The major difference between MHF and 2TM methods is their sensibility to measure the power law across different order of moments. The MHF results are often masked by H and for high value makes very hard to calculate with accuracy α and C_1 . This is especially true when C_1 is low (< 0.05) where the error in the fitting gets bigger than the value itself.

Figure 3: 2TM of LRO LOLA DEM 118 m filtered out upper 10 km (Regime A). Across scales between 236 m and 272 km. For q^{th} moments of order between 1.1 and 2 with an increment of 0.2. For 20 values of η between exponential -1 and 1.

The results found are shown in Table 1 and compared with previous results [1,2,9]. The parameters α and C_1 are almost equivalent for both regime, despite previous results showing major differences.

	A	B
H smoothness	1.26 ± 0.002	0.051 ± 0.022
	0.88 ± 0.002	0.226 ± 0.002
α dispersion	1.63 ± 0.015	1.68 ± 0.013
	1.70 ± 0.3	1.40 ± 0.1
C_1 sparseness	0.064 ± 0.001	0.076 ± 0.001
	0.02 ± 0.04	0.03 ± 0.01

Table 1: Summary of the multifractal parameters on the Moon at small scale (domain A) fr and large scale (domain B) from our study using 2TM from [3,4] (in white) and the usual MHF analysis from [1] (in gray). The Hurst exponent H is estimated using the Power Spectral Density in our case. Error comes from the covariance matrix of the polynomial fit.

Conclusion and perspectives: We have demonstrated that the method 2TM is able to fit the multifractal parameter to describe the topography. Contrarily to the most common method MHF, we find that the smallest scale domain (< 10 km) is still multifractal. This show the limitation of the MHF method, especially when H is large.

This new result is in agreement with the observation that the lunar topography is intermittent with rough and smooth regions, even a scale < 10 km. It is also in agreement with the local apparent variations in H and other multifractal parameters [10].

This work paves the way to estimate the local multifractal properties that is very promising to decipher the competition between the different geological processes carving the lunar surface (cratering, space weathering, volcanic effusive and explosive processing). It also allows a better description of the surface interface slope distribution, important to understand the volatile exchange, but also to better describe the light-matter interaction (from UV, visible, IR and radar) in order to develop a new generation of remote sensing tools.

References:

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